

»To advocate for positive change in the policies, culture, and environment that affect the quality of training, well-being, and employment conditions of early career researchers«

Eurodoc

Annual Report

2023/24

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Board for the Eurodoc Administration 2023/2024

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eurodoc

The European Council of Doctoral
Candidates and Junior Researchers

Foreword

Dear All,

Another intense term comes slowly to a closure with many memorable moments, meaningful outputs, and impactful activities now lying behind us. We had gone into the term with a very ambitious work plan and a rich collection of aims. It might not be completely surprising that not all of those ambitions have come to full fruition, yet we hope to have, once again, shown Eurodoc's effectiveness and the crucial work all the Eurodoc volunteers are doing for advancing and improving the working environment of PhD candidates and early career researchers. Looking back on the concluding term, the board and administration have proven themselves to be a well-balanced group, able to carry forward the warm and welcoming atmosphere the previous boards have built. It is in the precarious nature of early career researchers' positions and the voluntary nature of the work in a volunteers' organisation that resignations cannot always be avoided, thus completing the term with the entire elected team is a testimony to the mutual support and positive environment that has been fostered.

For this term, the administration sought to engage in a number of key areas crucial to the association, its mission and vision. For one, looking inwards, much was done to improve the organisational basis, including the information management, the financial management and the transparency towards its member organisations. Although there has been limited capacity to explore more stable outside financing, organisational sustainability has been a constant focus. For another, looking outwards, the representation activities and the engagement of European stakeholders and policymakers have been further broadened and steps have been taken towards further improving the effectiveness of these European engagements. Thus, a cornerstone of our work has been the increased activities in third party-funded projects and consortia, which provide additional financial means for Eurodoc's ongoing activities and offer crucial opportunities for policy impact. Beyond project work, the exchanges and collaborations with other European stakeholder organisations have been enhanced, in particular with regards to other representatives of early and mid-career researchers.

We have furthermore worked towards further enhancing the engagement with our members, including through individual meetings of board members with National Association delegates, through events and workshops organised by Eurodoc, and through the continuation of the regularly scheduled NA meetings. Moreover, the inputs received from the Advisory Board was increased and deepened, particularly through the long-term planning of important topics in addition to the ad-hoc meeting culture for consulting meetings that are crucial in such a dynamic environment as the European academic sector. These many activities are well visible in the rich variety of communication activities, but also in the results of the different working groups.

This term is ending, but this is just another new beginning for Eurodoc. We look forward to meeting all of you at the AGM 2024 in person or online and are open to new exciting projects and collaborations.

Eurodoc Administrative Board members

*Sebastian Dahle, Pil Maria Saugmann,
Hannah Schoch, Devriş İşler,
Sara Pilia, Aleksandra Lewandowska*

Contents

1 Eurodoc objectives	4
2 Eurodoc Members & Observers	4
2.1 National Associations (NAs)	4
2.2 Observers	4
3 Eurodoc Administration Members	5
3.1 Administrative Board	5
3.2 Secretariat	5
3.3 Advisory Board	6
4 Eurodoc Activities 2023/2024	6
4.1 Focus topics	7
4.2 Organisation-related goals	8
4.3 Policy-related goals	11
4.4 Project-related goals	11
4.5 Communication-related goals	14
4.6 Stakeholder-related goals	14
4.7 Contributions from the Working Groups	16
4.8 Contributions from the Task Forces	17
4.9 Contributions to CoARA	18
5 Eurodoc Representations and Missions in 2023/2024	19
6 Eurodoc External Communication	21
6.1 Website	22
6.2 Social Media	23
6.3 Newsletters	23

1 Eurodoc objectives

Eurodoc shall pursue the following objectives according our [statute](#), [mission and vision](#):

- (a) **To represent** doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level in matters of education, research and professional development of their careers.
- (b) **To advance** the quality of doctoral programmes and the standards of research activity in Europe.
- (c) **To promote** the circulation of information on issues regarding young researchers, **organize** events, **take part** in debates, and **assist** in the elaboration of policies about Higher Education and Research in Europe.
- (d) **To establish** and **promote** cooperation between national associations representing doctoral candidates and junior researchers within Europe. Eurodoc shall not interfere with the competences of its member organisations in respect of all national matters and issues.

2 Eurodoc Members & Observers

2.1 National Associations (NAs)

Belgium (PhD society), Czech Republic (SK RVŠ), Denmark (PAND), Finland (FUURT), France (CJC), Germany (THESIS), Hungary (DOSZ), Ireland (IFUT and USI), Italy (ADI), Latvia (LJZA), Lithuania (LSYR), Netherlands (PNN), Norway (SiN), Poland (KRD), Portugal (ABIC), Romania (ANOSR), Slovakia (ADS), Slovenia (MA), Spain (FJI-Precarios), Sweden (SNPA and SFS/SFSDK), Switzerland (actionuni), Ukraine (YSC), and Azerbaijan (AYSPMU)

2.2 Observers

Individuals: Turkey, Bosnia-Herzegovina

Organisations: Georgia (YSDCG)

Fig. 1 Eurodoc's Members and Observers on a map

3 Eurodoc Administration Members

The Eurodoc administration consists of the Administrative board, Secretariat and Advisory board members.

3.1 Administrative Board

The Administrative Board is Eurodoc's regular executive body that represents, leads and administers Eurodoc's daily activities and follows the decisions adopted by the General Meeting.

Position	Person	Association
President	Sebastian Dahle	Slovenia/MA
Vice-President	Pil Maria Saugmann	Sweden/SFS/SFSDK/SNPA
Treasurer	Devriş İşler	Spain/FJI-Precarios
Secretary	Hannah Schoch	Switzerland/actionuni
General Board Member	Sara Pilia	Italy/ADI
General Board Member	Aleksandra Lewandowska	Poland/KRD

3.2 Secretariat

Secretariat members are part of the administration who help to carry on the Eurodoc annual goals, coordinated by the Administrative Board.

Position	Person	Association
Secretariat Coordinator	Linnéa Carlsson	Sweden/SFS/SFSDK
External Communication Coordinator	Anna Pavelieva	Ukraine/YSC
Campaign Officer	Yuliia Zahumenna	Ukraine/YSC
Newsletter Coordinators	Iryna Gumeniuk	Ukraine/YSC
French Language Officers	Magali Weissgerber & Magali Cécile Bertrand	France CJC & Switzerland/Actionuni
Webmaster	Khrystyna Zub	Ukraine/YSC
Equal Opportunities Officer	Sara Pilia	Italy/ADI
Data manager	Tamara Mahanova	Ukraine/YSC
WG Doctoral Training Coordinator	Karl Kilbo Edlund	Sweden/SFS/SFSDK
WG Employment Conditions and Welfare Coordinator	Joanna Rutkowska	Switzerland/Actionuni
	Anastasiia Simakhova	Ukraine/YSC
WG Mental Health Coordinator	Mathias Schroijen	Belgium/OR
	Sara Willhammar	Sweden/ SFS/SFSDK
WG Open Science Coordinator	Maja Dolinar	Slovenia/MA

	Agnieszka Zyra	Poland/KRD
WG Research and Society Coordinator	Irina Dumitru	Romania/ Sweden
	Larysa Makaruk	Ukraine/RMU
WG Research Assessment & Career Paths Coordinator	Nicola Dengo	Italy/ADI
	Rimsha Naeem	Finland/ FUURT

3.3 Advisory Board

The Advisory Board supports the Administrative Board and other Eurodoc bodies with advice and facilitates the knowledge transfer between consecutive terms to assure the continuity of Eurodoc as an organisation.

Advisory board members for 2023/2024:

- Beata Zwierzynska (Poland)
- Giulia Malaguarnera (Italy)
- Iryna Degtyareva (Ukraine)
- Mathias Schroijsen (Belgium)
- Miia Ijäs-Idrobo (Finland)
- Oleksandr Berezko (Ukraine)

4 Eurodoc Activities 2023/2024

In this Annual Report, we describe the activities based on Eurodoc's Annual Goals, which were approved by the AGM held in Uppsala (Sweden) in 2023.

The annual goals that Eurodoc sets out for itself and its administration to achieve in any given term of course follow Eurodoc' [mission and vision](#) statements:

Eurodoc's mission

"To advocate for positive change in the policies, culture and environment that affect the quality of training, well-being and employment conditions of early career researchers."

Eurodoc's vision

"A fair and sustainable research culture where early career researchers (ECRs) are treated with respect and have access to long-term and stable career pathways."

More precisely, according to its [statutes](#), Eurodoc shall pursue the following objectives:

- (a) To represent doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level in matters of education, research and professional development of their careers.
- (b) To advance the quality of doctoral programmes and the standards of research activity in Europe.
- (c) To promote the circulation of information on issues regarding young researchers, organise events, take part in debates, and assist in the elaboration of policies about Higher Education and Research in Europe.
- (d) To establish and promote co-operation between national associations representing doctoral candidates and junior researchers within Europe. Eurodoc shall not interfere with the competences of its member organisations in respect of all national matters and issues.

4.1 Focus topics

A few topics have developed over the past terms and qualify for particular attention beyond the activities in and through Eurodoc's working groups. These topics are precarity and career development, open science, research assessment, academic freedom, and Eurodoc's own internal organisation. Since these topics are often addressed in different Eurodoc contexts, it can be that the description of this administration's Eurodoc activities related to the set objectives for the respective topics are found in a number of sections in this report. We tried to cross-reference further relevant sections in each description.

4.1.1 Precarity and career development

P1.1 – Review (landscaping) the employment status and working conditions for ECRs in Europe, and provide policy recommendations for the improvement.

This topic relates to employment specifically, but more generally to framework conditions for researcher careers. Eurodoc has and will continue its work within the project SECURE, advocacy for EU-driven or -mediated solutions, further dissemination and follow-ups for the ISE Manifesto, and in particular also in CoARA. The Postgraduate Workers' Organisation (PWO) of Ireland published the report "[Workers in all but name, pay, and conditions](#)" (February 2024), which takes the report "[EURODOC survey on the structure of the doctorates across Europe](#)" (2018-20) as a key reference study. They held a meeting in April, inviting other European PhD and early career researchers' organisations in Europe to discuss future Europe-wide action on the issues raised in that report. Eurodoc is in direct contact with PWO and will follow up on them to ensure good collaboration. For further work done on precarity and career development, see also the work described under 4.4.2, 4.7.2, 4.7.6, 4.9.

4.1.2 Open Science

P1.2 – Develop a joint basis for adequate training, rewarding system and implementation of Open Science instruments for ECRs.

A strong topic of Eurodoc's work over many years already has concerned Open Science in all its aspects. A policy paper on Open Science was released early in the new mandate. Throughout the year, Eurodoc has continued to contribute on this focus topic, in the Horizon Europe project OPUS, and in the Erasmus+ project OPTIMA and Open4UA, OPTIMA subject to its being granted.

Eurodoc has over the course of the year reviewed the Open Science ambassador program. While some modules still hold a high quality after 5 years, others were found to be outdated and in some cases the video material unfortunately was too corrupted. Thus, the conclusion had been not to revive the ambassador program, as a full revision of the program would require resources that Eurodoc does not possess at the moment. Furthermore, many institutions have themselves taken up the training of researchers in open science and/or designating ambassadors.

4.1.3 Research Assessment

The assessment of research and researchers has gained a lot of attention across Europe in the past two years, as it has been identified both as a crucial leverage point to improve the situation of researchers and as an obstacle for its existing shortcomings. We devoted strong efforts to the CoARA coalition, where Eurodoc is part of almost all working groups to run a working group. Further we will contribute at external forums on the topic, such as the KRECon conference. See especially also the work described under 4.4.2.

4.1.4 Academic Freedom

P1.3 – Advocate for more specific regulations and legislation that establishes academic freedom as a fundamental right for researchers in an enforceable way.

The definition and enforceable protection of Academic Freedom has been a matter of Eurodoc discussions in past years, triggered by occurrences i.a. in Hungary, Poland, Slovenia, and Sweden.

We continued and will continue with the process of providing inputs to policymakers and with continued engagement with the European parliament, as well as related activities. Thus, for example, we ensured that there was a question on academic freedom in the [Survey of EP candidate lists' views on Research and Innovation](#), conducted by Initiative for Science in Europe (ISE) together with the EURODOC, ICoRSA, MCAA and YAE.

Eurodoc has throughout the term put focus on how threats and challenges to academic freedom is enhanced by the precarious situation of doctoral candidates and early career researchers and by their lack of formal representation. This is an issue that is often overlooked, and thus, for their submission to the [Conference \(FOHE-BPRC5\) The Future of Higher Education – Bologna Process Researchers'](#), the vice president and the secretary sent in an abstract titled "Frameworks for Doctoral Education: Academic Freedom of Doctoral Candidates Across Europe". In this article, they survey the frameworks for doctoral education in 10 European countries, among other things highlighting that the inclusion of doctoral candidates in academic governance is in many places very weak, which in turn risks infringing on their academic freedom. This article will be published in *European Higher Education Area 2030: Bridging Realities for Tomorrow's Higher Education* edited by A. Curaj, R. Pricopie, C. M. Hâj (Springer Nature, Fall 2024).

4.1.5 Internal organisation

The internal organisation of Eurodoc has been subject to continuous improvements in the past. This term, we particularly focused on better documentation and information flow as crucial points for compliance with the statutes as well as for the sustainability of the association and for a more efficient use of our capacities. For details, see particularly 4.2.1., 4.2.2., 4.2.3.

4.2 Organisation-related goals

4.2.1 Information management: Improve the information management to ensure findability and easy, intuitive access to both Eurodoc's internal and public resources.

O1.1 – Define access levels for the different contents and resources; O1.2 – Revise the drive and archive structure for intuitive findability and accessibility. O1.5 – Implement an HRM system to comply at minimum with the following conditions: O1.5.1 – Provide a database of individuals contributing to Eurodoc, for future acknowledgements. O1.5.2 – Provide an inventory of contact email addresses available for all members and observers, to comply with Internal Regulations article 10(2).; O1.5.3 – Provide an inventory of email lists, for each list including the purpose of the list, public/internal use, and the moderator's contact details, to comply with Internal Regulations article 10(1a).

The entire G-Drive structure for Eurodoc has been revised and re-organized. The structure and levels of access have been further standardised and defined. For the inventory on e-mail lists, the Eurodoc G-Drive folder structure, and the contributors to statements, the documentation is available [here](#) for the NAs. Moving forward, compliance and further iterative improvement will be absolutely key to ensure its usefulness. The database of individuals contributing has not been completed. However, we have implemented that for each text written all the contributors as well as the editors are always listed with their Orcid number.

Furthermore, on the Eurodoc G-Drive, templates for the following have been created to make work more efficient and to standardise layout:

- Google slides:
 - Certificate
 - Introduction to Eurodoc
 - Template Presentation

- Google docs:
 - Article Template
 - Eurodoc Statement
 - Minutes
 - Mission Report
 - MR Communication (Mission Report Communication)

These can equally be accessed by the NAs: on the Eurodoc G-Drive → drive “09_00 Shared Platform” via right click → hover over google docs or google slides → select ‘From a template’ → select template you need.

O1.3 – Revise structure and content on website and Zenodo; C1.3 – Improving the visibility of Eurodoc WGs and their members on the Eurodoc website.

The Zenodo community ownership has been transferred to the board and the structure and the uploads have been restructured. The revision of the structure and content of the website still has to be tackled.

O1.4 – Implement a comprehensive list of official positions (statements), publicly available on the website, to comply with Internal Regulations article 13(1c)

Completed. A comprehensive list of official statements is available [here](#) for the NAs. However, the information is not yet publicly available.

O1.6 – Implement an inventory of Eurodoc’s involvements, including but not limited to delegations, membership in other organisations’ advisory boards, commitments as associated partner or with other contributions to projects

The board has started to create a more comprehensive overview, available to the administration. The next board should continue this work and keep the overview updated.

4.2.2 Organisational culture (O2): Further enhance the affirmative and collaborative nature of Eurodoc’s organisational culture and implement activities for the gender equality plan

O2.1 – Implement and amend the Gender equality plan; O2.2 – Implement further measures to support a good organisational culture

For both objectives, see 4.8.2.

4.2.3 Efficient internal communication (O3): Restructure communication for enhanced efficiency and implement additional approaches for effective collaboration

O3.1 – Transfer the internal communication to Slack, including all working groups and taskforces, as well as parts of the interaction with the NA delegates.

Internal communication by the board has been fully transferred to Eurodoc slack in addition to e-mails, and virtual or in-person meetings. Working groups and taskforces have so far not been transferred to Slack, since its feasibility and the actual take-up by the members is not clear.

The board is proposing changes to the statutes and internal regulations to the 2024 AGM that update the forms and means with which votes by the board can be carried out, in particular between board meetings. This will make internal communication significantly more streamlined.

O3.2 – Split channels [announce], [consultation], and [voting] according to the outcomes of the AGM 2023.

The mailing lists for communication with the NAs and interested people have been split into:

- announce [announce@eurodoc.net):
 - purpose: broad dissemination of information that is of general interest
 - includes: members of NAs, board, secretariat, Eurodoc delegates, affiliated and interested persons
- NA voting [na-voting@eurodoc.net):
 - purpose: singular use for NAs voting on proposal by Eurodoc
 - includes: all current NA delegates to Eurodoc and the board
- NA consultation [na-consultation@eurodoc.net):
 - purpose: slightly broader dissemination of key information, documents etc. where Eurodoc needs the NAs' input, opinions, responses or key information for NAs pertaining to Eurodoc matters to ensure that the NA is well-informed and has as best of a chance to respond
 - includes: NA voting, board, Advisory Board, presidents or info e-mails of NAs unless explicitly asked to be removed

Further details on the mailing lists can be found [here](#). The former consultation mailing list has been retired as it was not feasible to sort out who was still supposed to be on the list, seen as it had not been consistently updated when delegates stepped down from their role.

03.3 – Establish additional measures to provide low-barrier opportunities for NAs' engagement.

In order to provide low-barrier opportunities for NA engagement, Eurodoc has continued with NA meetings throughout this term. Furthermore, the board meetings this year had a structure where the first part was closed and only for board members and the second part was open to the NA. Both of these provided important touch points with the NAs to ensure contact and knowledge exchange.

Crucially also, Eurodoc's vice president has with the support of the working group coordinator Nicola Dengo carried out individual meetings with 20 of Eurodoc's NAs. These meetings have served to replace the annual questionnaire and instead allow Eurodoc to gain a better understanding of how the NAs function, what challenges they experience, and how Eurodoc can better support them, as well as what their strengths and successes are. This personalised contact, rather than the survey, has been experienced as very helpful and insightful.

Furthermore, contact has been established with the national association of Croatia, Penkala, who are applying for membership status at the upcoming AGM.

4.2.4 Strategic stakeholder engagement (O4): Implement a strategic approach to stakeholder engagement

O4.1 – Finalise the stakeholder analysis; O4.2 – Produce a comprehensive stakeholder engagement plan

Eurodoc has moved forward with the work on the stakeholder mapping and with a more comprehensive stakeholder engagement plan that includes both the EU as well as the EHEA. This work can hopefully be consolidated by the next administration. In particular, it might be useful to make the stakeholder mapping publicly available at least within Eurodoc.

4.2.5 Sustainability (O5): Implement activities to ensure Eurodoc's continuity, sustainability and financing

During 2024 Eurodoc started preparing documentation for an application to acquire funding from the Council of Europe's European Youth Foundation. However, it is unclear whether Eurodoc fulfils the requirements or not. Thus, following the advice of previous recipients of funding from the foundation,

Eurodoc is preparing to approach the foundation for further guidance on how to proceed if possible. Due to time constraints the application Eurodoc did not submit for an Eurodoc led COST action.

4.2.6 Accounting revision (O6): Revise accounting and finance

O6.1 Revise accounting with external consultant; O6.2 Revise financial reports 2022/2023; O6.3 Feedback rounds with NAs & preparation of extraordinary GM for approval

Despite all efforts, no external consultancy contacted in the first 6 months of the term agreed to revise our accounting practices and support us in setting up better aligned procedures. Correspondingly, the revision was taken on by the board members without professional support.

The bookkeeping was arranged on a yearly basis, holding both bank accounts, a recording of membership fees invoiced and paid, a disambiguation into project total sums, assignment of transaction category, as well as an automated generation of balance sheet and monthly cash flow charts. The yearly accounting files also include an overview dashboard, where the bank account and project balances are highlighted at the beginning of the fiscal year, at the point of the AGM, and at the end of the fiscal year.

In order to determine the financial status of all ongoing projects, all bank accounts were reviewed back until including 2021, transcribing all transactions into the bookkeeping template.

The project-specific accounting and record-keeping was set up using a simplified bookkeeping template for projects' sub-accounts. Here, the project main sum is broken down into cost categories.

For a meaningful and transparent presentation of each board's work, a further template was generated that showcases the incomes and expenses across a variety of cost categories as well as the projects. This cash flow statement on a mandate-timed basis is also reproduced in the revised template for the draft budget, thus making a comparison and planning more intuitive.

Finally, a briefing document for the Eurodoc auditors has been produced in order to lead them in a structured way through the auditing process, for which they have been provided with all the necessary documentation, including bank statements, accounting files, and project sub-accounts.

In the revision of the previous accounting practices, it became apparent that the membership payment procedure remains unintuitive to a number of National Associations, and that in the past, updated invoices according to granted reductions have occasionally been missed. It has therefore become clear, that improvements to the understanding of the process as well as the consistent implementation are needed, whereas the retrospective nature of the payments is to be kept up in light of the financial situation of some of the member organisations. Correspondingly, the topic has been the matter of discussion at one of the structured NA meetings of the term.

Furthermore, an explanation of the membership fee payment procedure has been created for easier understanding of the process: ["How to pay Eurodoc Membership Fees"](#)

4.3 Policy-related goals

P1.1 – Review (landscaping) the employment status and working conditions for ECRs in Europe, and provide policy recommendations to the improvement.

See 4.1.1 and 4.4.2. for related work.

P1.2 – Develop a joint basis for adequate training, rewarding system and implementation of Open Science instruments for ECRs.

See 4.1.2, 4.4.3, 4.4.4, 4.4.5., 4.7.4 and 4.9 for details.

P1.3 – Advocate for more specific regulations and legislation that establishes academic freedom as a fundamental right for researchers in an enforceable way.

See 4.1.4 for details.

P1.4 – Support Ukrainian and other researchers at risk in the time of war and as long as it is needed.

See 4.4.5 for details.

4.4 Project-related goals

The project-related goals are directly taken from the work plan of each of the ongoing projects, which had been aligned with the organisational goals, vision and mission during the application phase. On the following pages, the activities and outcomes are presented for each of the projects, these are OPUS, SECURE, Open Research Europe, OPTIMA, and Open4UA.

4.4.1 OPUS

Eurodoc is a consortium member of The Open and Universal Science ([OPUS](#)) project. The OPUS project is an EU-funded project implemented by an eighteen-organisations consortium led by The Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands ([PLOCAN](#)). The project started in September 2022 and will end in August 2025. The main aim of the project is to develop coordination and support measures to reform the assessment of research and researchers at Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) toward a system that incentivises and rewards researchers to engage in Open Science practices. The term "Open Science" is understood to refer to practices that provide open access to research outputs, early and open sharing of research, participation in open peer review, measures to ensure reproducibility of results, and involving all stakeholders in co-creation. In this proposal, the interpretation of Open Science is employed with a specific focus on reforming the research assessment system to incentivize and reward researchers to adopt these practices. OPUS employs a three-tiered approach to ensure representation and consensus building of key stakeholder groups in the Open Science ecosystem. The OPUS consortium comprises a number of organisations, including research institutions, professional associations, industry bodies, and experts in project management, public relations and open science. There are many steps which need to be done within the project. First of all a comprehensive state-of-the-art review of existing literature and initiatives for Open Science was already conducted. A comprehensive set of tools are being developed to implement Open Science at RPOs and RFOs. Realistic indicators and metrics are also being discussed and developed to monitor and drive Open Science at RPOs and RFOs. The interventions and indicators and metrics will be tested via Action plans in pilots at RPOs and RFOs .

Eurodoc particularly collaborates in the state of the art on Open Science incentives, metrics, and indicators, as well as in drafting and disseminating policy recommendations. There have already been organised kick-off meetings and Annual General Meeting in November 2023 in Prague, in which Eurodoc representatives participated. The next OPUS AGM is planned also in November 2024 in Bucharest. Besides that there are also organised biweekly meetings with project partners which Eurodoc also participates in.

4.4.2 SECURE

Eurodoc is a full partner in the "[SECURE - Sustainable Careers for Researchers Empowerment](#)", aimed to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common Research Career Framework that offers a suite of options to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers with the aim of improving research careers and reducing

career precarity. The original plan was somehow overrun by the EU Commission first (July) and the Council after (December), with the publication of the Council Recommendation on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe. The consortium, with the effective support of Eurodoc, analysed the document recommendation by recommendation, and collaborated effectively in drafting a [Researchers Career Framework](#) that translates the Council recommendations into living principles and implementable practical suggestions (P.2.2.1). On the other hand, the research we conducted around the concept of tenure track and the analysis of different best practices led to the development of 9 basic principles that are needed to inform any [tenure track-like models](#) in different contexts and legal frameworks (P.2.2.2). Along this core work, Eurodoc participated in the drafting of the initial policy briefs, and in many dissemination and outreach activities of the project (P.2.2.3, P.2.2.4).

4.4.3 Open Research Europe (ORE)

Eurodoc is an expert partner in the “Open Research Europe” (ORE) project, an Open Access Publishing Platform, launched in the spring of 2021 by the European Commission. The platform is a significant step toward Open Science in Europe as it promotes preprints, open peer review, reproducibility, etc, and the role of Eurodoc is to ensure that the voice of ECRs is heard during its development and implementation. As an expert partner, Eurodoc participates in ORE project team and communication team meetings, organises various events, and provides recommendations. In the reporting period, Eurodoc particularly organised a [dedicated workshop on ORE](#) within the frames of the KRECon conference at the National Library of Technology (NTK) in Prague, Czechia, on November 9, 2023. Also, ORE was presented and discussed during the Eurodoc Lunchtime Webinar “Eurodoc advancing open science: ORE, OPTIMA, and Open4UA projects” on October 25, 2023. Finally, Eurodoc successfully conducted a [Short Survey on Multilingualism in Research Publishing](#) from November 2023 - December 2024 to inform EU policymakers and the ORE team about the experience and attitudes of the members of the international research community regarding multilingualism in the publishing of research. Almost 900 researchers from all over the world participated in the survey. The survey data will be processed and published as an open-access research paper later in 2024.

4.4.4 OPTIMA

Eurodoc is a full partner in the Open Practices, Transparency and Integrity for Modern Academia ([OPTIMA](#)) project that implements Open Science practices in Ukraine to improve the quality of National higher education services. The role of Eurodoc in the project is to advise on all the project activities, assist in the creation of an international online community of peer reviewers, and act as speakers and workshop leaders at project events (all on a volunteer basis). Due to the war in Ukraine, OPTIMA was prolonged for one year till mid-January 2025. Despite that, the project is successful, and Eurodoc’s participation is effective. In the reporting period, Eurodoc representatives delivered presentations and led workshops at the OPTIMA events in Nice (France) and Graz (Austria). Also, Eurodocers took part in shaping the community of peer reviewers at [Peers.International](#), project’s open peer review platform.

4.4.5 Open4UA

Eurodoc acts as a [partner](#) in the Open Science for Ukrainian Higher Education System ([Open4UA](#)) Erasmus+ project. The project has started in January 2023 and will end in October 2026. The main aim of Open4UA project is to advance the growth of Ukraine’s knowledge-driven economy for the post-war recovery by reforming the higher education (HE) system. That will be achieved by prioritising Open Science (OS) across different levels (from National policies to individual researchers), which is reflected in the project objectives. The mentioned objective focuses on fostering National reform on OS for the Higher Education system modernisation and EU integration by supporting legislation amendments based on the orchestrated National consensus.

The Kick-off Meeting which was held online in January was the first official meeting of consortium partners. During the meeting each of the consortium partners had an opportunity to briefly present the organisation which one represents. The valuable input was given by the Project Officer, who shared important formal guidelines which should be implemented during the project realisation.

One goal of the project was organising workshops with the participation of project partners and external experts. By now three workshops have already been organised. These workshops involved training, open discussions, and international exchange of experiences to seek legal solutions regarding changes in the higher education and science law that could be implemented in Ukraine. The main aim was to improve the ossified higher education system that requires changes. Both workshops “How to get started with the implementation of Open Science nationally?” organised at TU Delft and workshop “Driving reforms: from drafts to legislative actions”, which were held in March 2024 in the Netherlands at Delft University of Technology and in Brussels at Université libre de Bruxelles were surely a milestones in achieving that. Eurodoc representatives had a great pleasure to participate in that events. The possible integration of Open Science principles with progressive approaches to research assessment reflecting to CoARA's principles in Ukrainian higher educational system reality were shown and discussed during the workshop. The interesting idea introduced was also adopting Open Science practices within academic institutions, overcoming institutional barriers and leveraging policy for sustained change. During the workshop in Brussels Eurodoc presented the impact of Eurodoc's [Open Science Ambassadors' programme](#) in empowering ECRs to lead the transition towards Open Science. It was wondered how effective legislation could adopt Open Science Practices, including the role of policy in overcoming barriers and fostering a culture of accessibility and collaboration in research. Interesting qualitative indicators and differences between research and researchers' assessment were presented. It was interesting to get deeper into the scopes of the Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) advocating for research assessment strategies which emphasise the value of research outputs and practices, fostering transparency, inclusivity and collaboration in the scientific community. Another approach which has been outlined was Coalition S (an initiative to make full and immediate Open Access to research publications a reality), providing initial information about scopes, and its commitment to Open Access and its influence on both senior and junior researchers. That overview was extremely useful for further discussions.

The third “Training workshop on Open Science and Advanced Research Assessment” was held in April at the University of Ljubljana in Slovenia. A four-day workshop was full of content about introducing Open Science policies and Research Assessment reforms particularly in Slovenia, which for sure can serve as an excellent example of how to respond to the current needs for the implementation of OS. During the workshop both perspectives of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, and from the University of Ljubljana management were presented. Participants had a chance to go through the reforms of Slovene legislation regarding Open Science and Research Assessment and at the same time Institutional reforms regarding Open Science and Research Assessment at University of Ljubljana. Meeting with the founding agency showed the opportunities for researchers as well as the methods of awarding scientific grants. Hands-on workshop on all practical aspects of research data management in a data archive, facilitated by the Social Science Data Archive was a good time to address practical questions regarding the publishing, dissemination and opening research outputs. The workshop ended with very fruitful discussions on recommendations which could be introduced in Ukraine both at national and institutional level.

The integral part of the workshops was drafting the policy proposals which advocate for advanced research assessment methods which could be implemented as well as the obstacles which could be met. As a result of all of the three workshops the [Recommendations for the Open Science and Research Assessment reforms in Ukraine](#) were drafted and published by the project partners.

4.5 Communication-related goals

C1 – Increasing the visibility of Eurodoc to remain a relevant stakeholder and partner

C1.1 – Publishing regularly on the Eurodoc website and in social media accounts; C1.4 – Promoting Eurodoc statements, surveys, and policy inputs; C1.6 – Publishing the monthly Eurodoc newsletter

The continued important efforts of the external communication team have been fundamental in increasing Eurodoc's visibility further. See chapter 6 for details.

C1.2 – Cultivating relationships with stakeholders in mass- and social media

The board has given a number of interviews and statements to Science|Business. Furthermore, the communication team has been making sure to engage and tag key stakeholders on social media. For more information, see chapter 6.

C1.8 – Inviting stakeholders to write articles for the Eurodoc website

The board has decided against following through with this idea as both quality and impartiality with articles written by other stakeholders could not be guaranteed.

C1.5 – Increasing transparency of Eurodoc actions, missions, and activities

See 4.2.3 for details on related activities to this goal.

C1.7 – Publishing the Annual report

The last few years, the annual report has been published on Zenodo together with an article on the website.

4.6 Stakeholder-related goals

C2 – Engaging with our major stakeholders and partners to advance our policy positions and focus topics and C2.1 – Engage with the European Commission, in particular actively contribute at the ERA Forum

The president and vice-president regularly met with representatives of MCAA, YAE, ICoRSA and ISE (C2.4, C2.5). Most notably, Eurodoc, MCAA, YAE, ICoRSA, and ISE have, under the latter's lead, been collaborating on a survey for the parties who are running candidates for the European parliament elections, which launched in May 2024. Many people, also from Eurodoc's member organisations, have contributed to this work.

Furthermore, Eurodoc continues to be active in ISE, with representation in both of the ISE working groups, and with Sebastian Dahle having recently been elected for the executive board of ISE for a mandate of three years.

In alignment with the annual goal C2.6 Eurodoc contributes actively to 6 of the 15 working groups in CoARA, 3 of which have a co-chair from Eurodoc. See 4.9 for the details on the contributions to each CoARA working group.

Eurodoc participated in both the annual meeting of EUA-CDE held in June 2023 and in EUA-CDE's Thematic Workshop on Leadership in and for doctoral education in February 2024. LERU was approached during the term in order to establish a closer collaboration which should continue next year. Eurodoc is contributing to several sessions at the ESOF 2024 which is the last one that will be organised by ScienceEurope (C2.9, C2.10).

In November, Eurodoc participated at the European Parliament's Science and Technology Options Assessment Panel (STOA-panel) high level conference 'Academic Freedom - The state of a fundamental value for Europe'. At this conference the 2023 version of the report "State of play of

academic freedom in the EU Member States” was presented.¹ Likewise, in February 2024 Eurodoc participated in the closing conference of the ROSiE Project, which focuses on Responsible Open Science in Europe. This event was part of the Academic Freedom Roundtable titled "Research Integrity for Open Europe," also organised by the STOA panel (C.2.2).

In the Council of Europe (CoE), Eurodoc is present/active in both the conference of international NGO's (CINGO) and the Steering Committee of Education (CD-EDU). CINGO brings together more than 400 international NGOs and works on issues related to human rights, the role of education in democracy, and ensuring a strong civil society. Much of CINGO's work takes place in its eight committees. Eurodoc is active in two of them: the committee on “NGOs as advocates for gender equality and women’s rights” and “Education for Democracy”. In CD-EDU, Eurodoc holds observer status. Here, Pii Maria Saugmann was elected to the bureau of CD-EDU as one of two representatives of the academic community for a mandate of 2 years.

Furthermore, also through the CoE, Eurodoc was invited to participate in the planning of the “Third Forum of History Education” which took place in Bologna May 15th-17th. Through this work, Eurodoc could strengthen its collaboration with both the International Alliances of Universities (IAU) and the European Students Union (ESU).

Within the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), Eurodoc has over the course of the last year used its observer status in the BFUG (C2.8) to work towards the long-term goal of Eurodoc becoming a consultative member. This would ensure that doctoral candidates are represented where decisions are made about their education.

At the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (see goal C2.7), Eurodoc was active in three task forces: [Research Careers, Recognition Credit](#), [Researcher Engagement and Adoption](#), [Semantic Interoperability](#). The work of these task forces has been concluded, and we thank Maja Dolinar, Sebastian Dahle, and Emanuelle Storti for their contributions. Following the end of the first period of the task forces, the board of Eurodoc supported Emanuelle Storti's application to become a member of the newly established EOSC taskforce [“EOSC Taskforce on Technical and Semantic Interoperability”](#) with a foreseen working period of 2024-2025.

4.7 Contributions from the Working Groups

4.7.1 Doctoral training

During the year, the Working Group on Doctoral Training has had six digital meetings of two hours each. The main work of the year has been to develop a draft statement on doctoral supervision. The statement is planned to be sent out on consultation in September.

4.7.2 Employment conditions and welfare

The Employment Conditions and Welfare Working Group focused on creating a resource for Early Career Researchers to find funding opportunities. The output is a blog post linking a table with information about funding resources in 9 European countries.

4.7.3 Mental health

The mental health working group has during the year had four digital meetings, each being two hours long. On the agenda there have been topics such as what tools NAs would think is useful within their national context, an outline for an article regarding mental health as well as dissemination of the ReMO STAIRCASE survey.

¹ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2023/740231/EPRS_STU\(2023\)740231_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2023/740231/EPRS_STU(2023)740231_EN.pdf)

4.7.4 Open science

Open science working group focuses on advocating policy recommendations for higher education and European research stakeholders on changing the academic culture towards a more open science one. During four working group meetings we had a great opportunity to discuss current needs of ECRs in the matter of Open science, potential actions and initiatives which could be undertaken. That was also a wonderful chance to think about the future goals and directions of Open Science WG. One of WG's goals was to evaluate and adjust the Open Science Ambassadors program. To do that it was necessary to evaluate the content and at the same time revitalize the program concept for the upcoming years. The Eurodoc Ambassadors program ran from March until August 2019. The course was designed by [Gareth O'Neill](#) (former Eurodoc President), who was responsible for setting up all the modules and inviting speakers, as well as preparing final exam questions and its evaluation, and [Ivo Grigorov](#), facilitated by [Roberta Moscon](#) on an Erasmus+ Staff Exchange, as a cooperation of Eurodoc and [Foster](#). A total number of [24 Eurodoc ambassadors](#) successfully completed the course. The participants in the Open Ambassador program were expected to act as ambassadors of Open Science in the research communities and disseminate the knowledge they acquired during the programs. The main objectives of the course were the following:

- Understand the basic principles and practices of Open Science
- Educate and train (early-career) researchers in Open Science
- Inform and engage research stakeholders about Open Science

The course consisted of 10 modules focusing on aspects of Open Science. The 10 modules included in the original Ambassador program were M1 Open Science, M2 Open Access, M3 Open/FAIR Data, M4 Open Peer Review, M5 Data Management, M6 Plan S, M7 Open Licensing, M8 Open Clouds, M9 Open Policies, and M10 Open Source.

The Ambassadors Programme proved to be a successful initiative in response to the demand for open science knowledge among early-career researchers. After a deep analysis it was established that there is a current need to expand and update the issues presented in the Eurodoc Ambassadors' Program if the program were to be renewed. As far as the approach and knowledge about open science had changed a lot from 2019, the amount of time and work required to develop the new concept exceeded the capacity of the working group. Detailed analysis of the Open Science Ambassador's program was conducted, formulated and shared with the board.

4.7.5 Research and Society

No meetings were held in the Research and Society working group.

4.7.6 Research Assessment and Career Paths

As the first stage, the Research Assessment and Career Paths performed a preliminary work aimed at creating a general reference scheme for researchers' career paths based on EURAXESS four career levels (R1 to R4) for each of the main assessment steps in an academic career – from doctoral education, to hiring, to obtaining grants. This was discussed in the first meeting of the WG, where it became clear that the scope of this was too vast to be tackled effectively in one take. Thus, the focus was readjusted to creating a pilot study on a highly problematic assessment step: the Habilitation. This was deemed to be a perfect candidate for the pilot study as it (i) can often be a make-or-break step in an academic career, (ii) it is a fundamental exercise of research assessment, (iii) is wildly inconsistent across the European higher education area. The WG's first step was to schematize the main cultural pillars the habilitation can stand for (e.g. doctor of science degree in Eastern Europe, Higher doctorates, the German habilitation, the French HDR, the Italian ASN, etc.). In a second step, we did a Europe-wide data gathering activity on existing Habilitation or Habilitation-like procedures. The group is currently compiling the information in a dedicated document and checking it. The next steps have to be determined.

4.8 Contributions from the Task Forces

4.8.1 Ukraine Taskforce

W1.1 Continued support for our colleagues in Ukraine for the time of the war and as long as needed; W1.2 Advocacy work towards the rebuilding of Ukraine's academia

Eurodoc has throughout the term tried to support the YSC and advocated for more designated support to the higher education and research sector in Ukraine. In July 2024, Eurodoc's president Sebastian Dahle and vice president Pil Maria Saugmann visited Kiyv. Here, among other things they met with regional representatives of YSC and listened to how the war had affected their private and professional lives. Their stories and reflections has enabled Eurodoc to throughout the term provide nuanced feedback in meetings and collaborations. Some of the crucial work done can be read up on here (selection):

- [Higher education and academic research are key elements for Ukraine's recovery](#)
- [Eurodoc president writes open letter to European Commission president Ursula von der Leyen](#)
- [Eurodoc and the Young Scientists Council at the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine sign a resolution following the roundtable of July 21st](#)
- [Meeting Early Career Researchers in Ukraine: 30% Fewer Young Scientists than before the War](#)
- [Eurodoc with and for Ukrainian academia: Visiting Kyiv during times of war](#)

Furthermore, Eurodoc has ensured that a specific question on the conditions of the Ukrainian higher education and research sector was included in the European Parliament survey.

4.8.2 Equality Taskforce

W2.1 Engage in the stakeholder board at the COST action VOICES; W2.3 Engage with ERA Action 5 Gender Equality and Inclusiveness; W2.2 Support the implementation and further development of the GEP; O2.1 – Implement and amend the Gender equality plan; O5.3 – Evaluate the effectiveness of the Equality Taskforce and submit recommendations on how to continue work on equality topics to the AGM 2024.

Among the many objectives related to the Equal Opportunities domain, Eurodoc has continued to coordinate the Stakeholders Board within the COST Action [VOICES](#). The main task has been that of supporting the consortium in the writing of a White Book that summarises the main research results and design a set of policy recommendations stemming from research-based reflections. This work is still ongoing, as the White Book is due by late 2025, and it was developed by the Equal Opportunities Officer supported by the vice president, through various meetings of the with the COST Action participants. These meetings were aimed and developing a basic knowledge of the EU policy debate around the topic of Gender Equality, of the workings of advocacy and policy advising within the EU research context. During the last 2-days meeting organised before the AGM, the Equal Opportunities Officer guided the COST Action participants in drafting a general outline of the White Book and the index of the first draft.

At the same time, the Equal Opportunities Officer participated in all the meetings called by the ERA Action 5 Expert group on Gender Equality and Inclusiveness (except the last one on May 23, due to tech reasons). The main task completed by the Expert Group was the drafting and presentation to the ERA Forum of a "EU Baseline on a Strategy for a Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct to counteract gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, in the EU Research and Innovation System". Thanks to Eurodoc participation in this group, the document, that the ERA Forum would like to push further to become a Commission Recommendation, includes some specific provisions aimed at protecting and supporting the doctoral candidates and early career researchers. Another meeting of the taskforce working on this document is planned for June 24.

Eurodoc's gender equality is in place, the next round of revisions is still outstanding. This will be tackled together with the Code of Conduct (see below).

02.2 – Implement further measures to support a good organisational culture

In addition to the continuation of conversations on the organisational culture and community spirit that Eurodoc wants to practise with and for its members and volunteers, two specific projects have been started:

European Directive on Whistleblowing

The board has taken notice of the [European directive on whistleblowing](#) that requires every organisation to have a way within the organisation to report ethical issues (financial crime, discrimination and harassment, etc). This directive is now given shape to by each of the countries, meaning that for Eurodoc, the Belgium legal framework is relevant, which stipulates that every organisation with more than 50 people related to the organisation must have a reporting channel to report ethical issues on the basis of non-retaliation, which includes the possibility to make it anonymous. The president and the secretary have engaged with the colleagues from MCAA, who handled their implementation, and from the respective European observatory for details and best practices of how the directive can be best implemented for Eurodoc as a volunteer-based, small albeit umbrella organisation with other organisations as members. This work will need to be continued by the next board.

Eurodoc Code of Conduct

The vice president and the secretary have begun drafting a Eurodoc Code of Conduct. It will be finalised with the new board over the summer to be presented to the NAs and voted on in the autumn.

4.9 Contributions to CoARA

Eurodoc is contributing to the Coalition of Advancing Research Assessment through participation in several of the working groups. In four of the working groups (CoARA Funders WG, CoARA EUA WG, CoARA Peer Review WG, CoARA Multilingualism WG) representatives of Eurodoc are actively involved as members of workstreams, and in two of the working groups (CoARA ECMR WG, CoARA ERIP) representatives of Eurodoc are serving as co-chairs. Besides this, Eurodoc also participates actively in CoARA general assemblies.

5 Eurodoc Representations and Missions in 2023/2024

Eurodoc representatives contributed to many conferences, meetings, and events. We tried to list all of them in the table below. You can find short descriptions and further information on each meeting [here](#).

Name of Eurodoc representative	Event	Date	Place/form
Pil Maria Saugmann	EUA-CDE annual meeting	14.-16.6.2023	Lathi, Finland
Sara Pilia	ERA Forum 5_2nd meeting	22.6.2023	online
Sebastian Dahle, Agnieszka Zyra	OPTIMA workshop	12.-16.6.2023	Nice, France
Sebastian Dahle, Pil Maria Saugmann	Visit of NA, Ministry etc.	19.-22.07.2023	Kyiv, Ukraine
Sebastian Dahle, Pil Maria Saugmann, Hannah Schoch, Aleksandra Lewandowska, Sara Pilia, Linnéa Carlsson,	Science Policy Workshop in Brussels	30.+31.8.2023	Brussels, Belgium

Anna Pavelieva, Joanna Rutkowska, Agnieszka Zyra			
Sebastian Dahle, Pil Maria Saugmann	Meeting with ESU	29.8.2023	Brussels, Belgium
Sebastian Dahle	VITAE conference	6.9.2023	online
Sebastian Dahle, Oleksandr Berezko	Open Science Fair	25.-27.9.2023	Madrid, Spain
Pil Maria Saugmann	EAIE	26.-27.9.2023	Rotterdam, Netherlands
Pil Maria Saugmann	CoE	28.-29.9.2023	Strasbourg, France
Oleksandr Berezko	F1000 webinar "How to maximize the impact of your research: an ECR's guide"	12.10.2023	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	INSPIRE	5.-6.10.2023	Budapest, Hungary
Pil Maria Saugmann, Sara Pilia	CINGO	9.-11.10.2023	Strasbourg, France, online
Pil Maria Saugmann	Melomanes	26.10.2023	Turku, Finland
Sebastian Dahle	YSC: 4th All-Ukrainian Forum of Young Scientists Councils	19.10.2023	online
Sebastian Dahle, Aleksandra Lewandowska, Pil Maria Saugmann	ORE workshop + KREcon	9.+10.11.2023	Prague, Czechia
Pil Maria Saugmann	STOA high level conference 'Academic Freedom - The state of a fundamental value for Europe'	29.-30.11.2023	Brussels, Belgium
Sebastian Dahle, Agnieszka Zyra	OPUS General Assembly	8.11.2023	Prague, Czechia
Sebastian Dahle	Conference "Modern Humanitarian Research of Young Scientists in a Globalized World: Challenges, Innovation, Security"	6.-7.11.2023	online
Aleksandra Lewandowska	BFUG Meeting	16-17.11.2023	Madrid, Spain
Sebastian Dahle, Nicola Dengo	ISE meeting on Careers	6.12.2023	Brussels, Belgium
Agnieszka Zyra	Open4UA kick-off meeting	25.01.2024	online
Pil Maria Saugmann	3rd Forum of History education planning meeting	2.2.2024	Bologna, Italy
Karl Kilbo Edlund	EUA-CDE	1.-2.2.2024	Prague, Czechia

Sebastian Dahle, Gledson Emidio	SECURE AGM	8+9.2.2024	Rijeka, Croatia
Pil Maria Saugmann, Agnieszka Żyra	Open4UA	15.02.2024	online
Aleksandra Lewandowska	BFUG	19-20.02.24	Brussels, Belgium
Aleksandra Lewandowska	ROSiE	21.02.2024	Brussels, Belgium
Pil Maria Saugmann	PAND meeting	8.2.2024	Copenhagen, Denmark
Pil Maria Saugmann	YSC winter school	21.2.2024	online
Sebastian Dahle, Pil Maria Saugmann	MCAA conference	14.-16.3.2024	Milan, Italy
Sebastian Dahle	EU R&I days	20.+21.3.2024	Brussels, Belgium
Pil Maria Saugmann	PAND GA	16.3.2024	online
Sebastian Dahle	Vključevanje in vrednotenje vidika spola na področju raziskav - Inclusion and evaluation of gender aspects in research	27.03.2024	Ljubljana, Slovenia
Pil Maria Saugmann, Devriş İşler	Open4UA	11.-13.03.2024	Delft, Netherlands
Agnieszka Zyra	Open4UA	14.-15.03.2024	Brussels, Belgium
Pil Maria Saugmann	CD-EDU	20.-22.03.2024	Strasbourg, France
Pil Maria Saugmann	FOHE-BPRC5	25-26.04-2024	Bucharest, Romania
Pil Maria Saugman	CINGO	8-10.04-2024	Strasbourg, France
Sebastian Dahle	MSCA conference	18.+19.4.2024	Mons, Belgium
Sebastian Dahle	UNICA communication seminar	23.4.2024	Ljubljana, Slovenia
Hannah Schoch	OECD	23.04.2024	Paris, France
Hannah Schoch	ERASMUS+ Jean Monnet conference	05.04.2024	online
Aleksandra Lewandowska	BFUG	11-12.04.2024	Brussels, Belgium
Aleksandra Lewandowska	UAM (Poland)	16.04.2024	Poznan, Poland
Pil Maria Saugmann	Philipp Schwartz and Inspireurope Stakeholder Forum 2024	18-19.04.2024	Berlin, Germany
Pil Maria Saugman	Widera_Infoday	22.04-2024	Brussels, Belgium
Pil Maria Saugmann, Nicola Dengo	ISE General Assembly	25-26.04-2024	Brussels, Belgium

Agnieszka Zyra	Open4UA	23-26.04.2024	Ljubljana, Slovenia
Pil Maria Saugmann	PRIDE	04.04.2024	Zurich, Switzerland
Pil Maria Saugmann	DOSZ: DOSZ Spring Wind Conference	03-05.2024	Budapest, Hungary
CoARA-ERIP Session: United Nations 4th STI Forum.	CoARA WG ERIP	10.05-2024	Online
Pil Maria Saugmann, Nicola Dengo, Hannah Schoch	Third Forum of History Education	15-17.5.2024	Bologna, Italy
Sebastian Dahle	ScienceEurope workshop: "Voting for Science: The Role of Science in Europe"	19.05.2024	Brussels, Belgium
Aleksandra Lewandowska	BFUG	28-30.05.2024	Tirana, Albania

6 Eurodoc External Communication

Since June 2023, Eurodoc's communication activities have focused on significant issues impacting the EU research community. In collaboration with organisations like MCAA, ICoRSA, and YAE, Eurodoc conducted a survey to assess the needs of Iranian scholars. A notable statement was published in response to the Swedish Government's decision to cut funding for development research. Eurodoc has also endorsed an open letter urging the European Commission to consider the needs of research and higher education in its lawmaking.

Further activities included hosting a series of lunchtime seminars and calling for solutions for Hungarian doctoral candidates and early career researchers to participate in Erasmus+ and Horizon Europe programmes.

Eurodoc has also reflected on co-authorship practices and advocated for high-quality employment conditions to ensure high-quality research output, emphasising the value of their work. During the reporting period, it published the second Open Science statement, endorsed the Lund Declaration, and conducted a short survey on multilingualism in research publishing. Celebrating internal achievements, Eurodoc awarded Eva Hnatkova for her outstanding contribution to the organisation.

Eurodoc's unwavering support for Ukrainian academia, demonstrated through visits to Kyiv during the war, has underscored the crucial role of a robust research and higher education sector for Ukraine's sustainable recovery, making a significant impact. Meetings with early career researchers in Ukraine revealed a 30% decrease in young scientists since the war began, emphasising the urgent need for support. An open letter stressed the importance of these issues and was addressed to European Commission president Ursula von der Leyen. Other notable efforts include commemorating a decade of war in Ukraine and stressing the importance of higher education and academic research for Ukraine's recovery.

6.1 Website

The list of website publications in 2023/2024 (29 pieces overall):

- [MCAA, Eurodoc, ICoRSA and YAE conduct a survey about the needs of Iranian scholars;](#)
- [Eurodoc publishes a statement on the Swedish Government's decision to cut the funding of development research;](#)

- [Eurodoc with and for Ukrainian academia: Visiting Kyiv during times of war;](#)
- [A strong research and higher education sector is crucial for a sustainable recovery of Ukraine;](#)
- [Meeting Early Career Researchers in Ukraine: 30% Fewer Young Scientists than before the War;](#)
- [Eurodoc president writes open letter to European Commission president Ursula von der Leyen;](#)
- [The Young Scientists' Council of Ukraine hosted Eurodoc's delegation in Kyiv;](#)
- [Reflections on co-authorship practices;](#)
- [High quality work requires high quality employment conditions;](#)
- [Eurodoc and the Young Scientists Council at the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine sign a resolution following the roundtable of July 21st;](#)
- [Eurodoc publishes its second Open Science statement and endorses the Lund Declaration;](#)
- [Eurodoc Met in the "Capital of Europe";](#)
- [Eurodoc Short Survey on Multilingualism in Research Publishing 2023;](#)
- [Eurodoc Family: Eva Hnatkova Awarded for Her Outstanding Contribution to Eurodoc;](#)
- [What is the future of research assessment?;](#)
- [Save the date – Eurodoc Lunchtime Seminar on Open Science Practices!](#)
- [Diversity and disabilities – or why academia still have a long way to go to be truly inclusive;](#)
- [Eurodoc calls for immediate solutions to allow Hungarian doctoral candidates and early career researchers to participate in Erasmus+ and Horizon Europe programmes;](#)
- [Eurodoc publishes its statement "The doctoral education – a research education";](#)
- [Research is research and doctoral education is a research education;](#)
- [Interview with Filippo Andrei from ADI;](#)
- [European histories, education, and the role of researchers as citizens;](#)
- [Eurodoc President Sebastian Dahle joined the Annual General Meeting of the SECURE project;](#)
- [Eurodoc launches its "Gender Equality in Research" Campaign;](#)
- [Eurodoc Commemorates a Decade of War in Ukraine;](#)
- [Higher education and academic research are key elements for Ukraine's recovery;](#)
- [A big question awaits: How to get started with the implementation of Open Science nationally?](#)
- [Eurodoc endorses the Open Letter: "European Research and Higher Education Organisations Call On Commission Not to Neglect Their Needs in Lawmaking";](#)
- [Eurodoc Conference 2024 ~ Towards a United European Research Area: The Ljubljana process and beyond.](#)

6.2 Social Media

Our followership grew on social media from July 2023 to May 29, 2024:

- **Facebook** page followers grew from 7179 to 7311 (+1.8%) for the previous year; there were 55854 post reaches, 9294 post engagement, 123 new page likes, 225 new readers.
- **Twitter** followers grew from 6429 to 6521 (+1.4%); there were 398 new tweets/retweets, 171942 tweet impressions.
- **LinkedIn** followers grew from 3415 to 3955 (+15.8%); there were 2105 page views, 1172 unique visitors, 53 custom button clicks, 540 new followers, 3032 reactions, 55 comments, 232 reposts.
- **YouTube** has 23 posts and the account has 170 followers.
- **Instagram** has 228 posts and the account has 220 followers.

Data calculated as of 29 May 2024.

In order to improve the social media campaign approaches, a Buffer account has been created for the scheduling of posts on four of the abovementioned social media channels.

6.3 Newsletters

The Eurodoc Newsletter is an important part of Eurodoc's communication activities, particularly towards external stakeholders, in 2023/2024 10 newsletters were sent out, serving as a vital tool to disseminate key information, updates, and achievements. This consistent communication helps to strengthen relationships with partners, policymakers, and the broader academic community, ensuring that Eurodoc's initiatives and contributions to the field of doctoral education and early-career research are widely recognized and supported. The structure of the newsletter was slightly changed and new sections were added.

Moreover, the management of the newsletter recipients have been improved by moving from a manually managed list into an email campaigning platform, including a self-signup form on the Eurodoc website and unsubscribe options in each of the newsletters sent.